

Tibetan Nonsectarianism (ris med)

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Mahayana Buddhism, Buddhist Traditions, Tibetan Buddhism

Tibetan nonsectarianism (ris med) describes a religious orientation in which the various philosophical and practice lineages of Tibetan Buddhism are understood as uniformly efficacious rather than as mutually exclusive competitors. Although many Tibetan Buddhists throughout history have adopted such an orientation, the concept was theorized most sophisticatedly in Kham and Amdo from the mid-nineteenth to early twentieth centuries, a period notorious for its political upheaval. Scholars have generally cited Jamgon Kongtrul Lodro Thaye Yonten Gyatso ('Jam mgon Kong sprul Blo gros Mtha' yas Rgya mtsho, 1813-1899), Jamyang Khyentse Wangpo ('Jam dbyangs Mkhyen brtse'i Dbang po, 1820-1892), and Orgyen Chokgyur Lingpa (O rgyan Mchog gyur Gling pa, 1829-1870), as three of the most important proponents of nonsectarianism as a self-consciously distinct, rather than implicit, orientation. All three were in close contact with one another and devoted their lives to reviving and preserving Tibetan Buddhist practices and teachings they feared were on the cusp of extinction, either due to active political suppression or popular indifference. The nonsectarian approach proved especially important in the late twentieth-century for Tibetan Buddhist teachers who had been forced into exile and sought to articulate a quasi-unified Tibetan Buddhist tradition that would be intelligible to the international world, and nonsectarianism has found a prominent place in the writings of modern luminaries as diverse as Kalu Rinpoche (Kar lu Rin po che, 1905-1989), Chogyam Trungpa (Chos rgyam Drung pa, 1939-1987), and the present Dalai Lama (Bstan 'dzin Rgya mtsho, 1935-present). There is not widespread agreement, either among scholars or Tibetan Buddhist teachers, about the precise use of nonsectarianism in the writings of the teachers mentioned above or in contemporary discourse. Indeed, the category is just as broad as "pluralism" or "ecumenicism." Jamgon Kongtrul was primarily concerned with the "eight chariots of accomplishment" (sgrub bryud shing rta chen po bryad) while contemporary teachers are more likely to emphasize the nonsectarian orientation with respect to the Nyingma, Kagyu, Gelug, and Sakya schools. Some argue that nonsectarianism is inclusivist, and was used by teachers of Kham and Amdo to subtly assert the superiority of their own local practices, while others believe nonsectarianism should be genuinely pluralistic, wherein the Tibetan Buddhist schools are treated as coequal. Some argue that nonsectarianism implies that a Tibetan Buddhist practitioner can draw on whichever practices would be useful to them individually, while others argue that one should follow exclusively a single lineage in one's own practice while respecting all others. These different readings have unsurprisingly yielded many different translations of ris med into English, of which "nonsectarianism" is the most common, but "ecumenicism," "universal," "without bias," "impartial," "an ecumenical approach," "eclecticism," "nonpartisan," and "nondiscrimination" have also been used. A further point of ambiguity is whether Tibetan nonsectarianism was exclusively an elite discourse in the nineteenth century, or if it included popular elements as well. Although Jamgon Kongtrul, Khyentse Wangpo, and Chokgyur Lingpa were all elite monastics, they sought to popularize practices that had henceforth been aimed primarily at fellow elite practitioners.

Date Range: 1840 CE - 1920 CE

Region: Kham and Amdo

Region tags: Asia, Amdo, China, Tibet

Nonsectarianism (ris med) in Eastern Tibet

参与者的状态

✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

来源

理解这一问题的书面资料：

- 来源 1: Gayley, Holly, and Schapiro, Joshua, eds. *A Gathering of Brilliant Moons: Practice Advice from the Rime Masters of Tibet*. United States: Wisdom Publications, 2017.
- 来源 2: Gardner, Alexander. *The Life of Jamgon Kongtrul the Great*. United States: Shambhala, 2019.
- 来源 3: Mathes, Klaus-Dieter, ed. *Nonsectarianism (ris Med) in 19th- and 20th-Century Eastern Tibet: Religious Diffusion and Cross-fertilization Beyond the Reach of the Central Tibetan Government*. Netherlands: Brill, 2021.

理解这一问题的在线资料:

- 来源1 URL: https://treasuryoflives.org/biographies/view/Jamgon-Kongtrul-Lodro-Taye/TBRC_P264
- 来源1 描述: Alexander Gardner's thorough biography of Jamgon Kongtrul Yonten Gyatso in the Treasury of Lives database.
- 来源2 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4kxd_VOHTal
- 来源2 描述: Ringu Tulku's 2006 lecture on ris med delivered in Brussels.
- 来源1 URL: https://treasuryoflives.org/biographies/view/Jamgon-Kongtrul-Lodro-Taye/TBRC_P264
- 来源1 描述: Alexander Gardner's thorough biography of Jamgon Kongtrul Yonten Gyatso in the Treasury of Lives database.
- 来源2 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4kxd_VOHTal
- 来源2 描述: A recording of a lecture delivered in 2006 by Ringu Tulku, an influential Buddhist teacher and scholar, on the "ris med approach."

相关的在线的原始文本资料库(使用原语言和/或翻译)

- 来源1 URL: <https://www.tsadra.org/digital-media/bilingual-library/>
- 来源1 描述: The Tsadra Bilingual Library contains an incredibly useful bilingual edition of Jamgon Kongtrul's entire Treasury of Knowledge. Requires app download.
- 来源2 URL: <http://purl.bdrc.io/resource/MW20880>
- 来源2 描述: High-quality scans of Jamgon Kongtrul's Autobiography.
- 来源3 URL: <http://purl.bdrc.io/resource/MW00KGO9825>
- 来源3 描述: Kongtrul's non-sectarian history of how Buddhism came to Tibet.

一般变量

成员/团体互动

其他宗教团体与该宗教之间有文化上的接触吗：

—是

Notes: Although the nineteenth-century practitioners of nonsectarianism were tangentially aware of

Islam, Christianity, and Chinese religions, they interacted most directly with Bon (Bon), which held both popular and institutional sway in nineteenth-century Kham and Amdo. Whether or not the nonsectarian approach extended to Bon practitioners was debated among authors who advocated a nonsectarian approach. For instance, Jamgon Kongtrul suggests in some of his writings that Bon is a valuable tradition that can be respected even in Buddhist terms; in other writings he argues that it is a deceptive tradition that Buddhists should oppose.

↳ 这种文化接触是竞争性的吗：

— 是

Notes: Yes, insofar as the Buddhists and Bonpos were at times competing for the same rituals and practitioners. However, the nonsectarian authors tended to take a more generous view of Bon than did other Buddhist authors at the time.

↳ 文化接触是兼容并包/多元的吗：

— 是

Notes: The greatest success of the nonsectarian movement was in bringing together the different Tibetan practice schools such that they began to think of themselves as a unified tradition rather than religious competitors. With respect to Bon, the nonsectarian authors tended to take a more generous view of Bon than did other Buddhist authors at the time, although not invariably. The nonsectarian was at its core a call for greater accommodation and pluralism of religious groups different than one's own within certain limits.

↳ 文化接触是中立的吗：

— 否

Notes: The Buddhists in eastern Tibet had far greater political, social, and institutional power than did Bonpos at the time.

↳ (在采样地区内)有暴力冲突吗：

— 否

Notes: Or, at least, not along religious lines. Although there was significant violence in Kham and Derge during this period, particularly when Gonpo Namgyel, the chieftain of Nyarong, conquered much of Kham from the 1840s-1865, Yudru Tsomu and others scholars have shown convincingly that his motives arose primarily out of his anger at the political treatment of his family and clan, and less over doctrinal or religious concerns.

↳ (与采样地区外的族群)有暴力冲突吗：

— 否

Notes: No, excluding the invasion of Gonpo Namgyel mentioned above, which I treat as an inner-Kham struggle. Although the nonsectarian authors struggled against the Lhasa occupation of Derge and other areas in Khams in the late nineteenth century, their protests never erupted into violent conflict.

该宗教团体有确认入会的一般性程序/制度吗：

— 否

Notes: The designation of certain nineteenth-century scholars and teachers as "nonsectarian" is an ex-post-facto scholarly designation before nonsectarianism truly became a self-aware movement in the twentieth century. Nevertheless, it is one that is consistently applied by both Buddhist and secular historians. However, there was no formal process or system for designating oneself as a practitioner of nonsectarianism, only an informal network of associations.

宗教团体积极宣教、招募新成员吗：

— 否

Notes: The nonsectarian authors actively propagated their position and sought to expand their ideological influence, but they didn't recruit new members insofar as there was no formal group or denomination for which people to join. Rather, they were trying to effect a paradigm shift in how different Buddhist traditions of practice regarded one another.

宗教有官方的政治支持吗：

— 是

Notes: Although Buddhist teachers who championed nonsectarianism could be found throughout the Tibetan Plateau, the concept received its greatest institutional support in the Kingdom of Derge, a small functionally-independent principality nestled between central Tibet and Qing territory. The Derge royal family propitiated Jamgon Kongtrul, Jamyang Khyentse Wangpo, and Chokgyur Lingpa, including by funding the printings of many of their works on nonsectarianism.

↳ 神职人员由政体出资供养吗：

— 是

Notes: Among other sources of revenue. The Derge royal family propitiated many of the monasteries associated with nonsectarian luminaries, as well as sponsored the printings of their works at considerable cost to the state. The royal family would also pay teachers to perform specific rituals, e.g. of healing, prosperity, or defense.

↳ 宗教基础设施由政体出资吗：

— 是

Notes: Among other revenue sources. Monasteries and nunneries were funded primarily through offerings, donations to the institution, and state funding, as well as labor carried out on monastic lands.

↳ 政体首脑和宗教领袖是同一个人吗：

— 否

Notes: No, not in eastern Tibet, although the highest lamas were also influential political figures.

↳ 政治官员相当于宗教官员吗：

— 否

Notes: Not officially, but important Buddhist teachers were also important political figures.

Sometimes individual teachers would also hold political offices (e.g. as a ritual specialist), but the two roles were broadly distinguished.

↳ 宗教仪式是由政体强制执行的吗：

— 否

Notes: Except insofar as a portion of required taxes were contributed to the monastic institutions.

↳ 政治律法和宗教法典大致重合：

— 否

Notes: The secular laws of Derge and other Tibetan polities were deeply informed by Buddhist values and categories, but there remained a distinction between the secular laws of state and those of the monastery.

↳ 政体提供优惠的经济待遇(比如免税)：

— 是

Notes: Large monasteries were empowered to levy their own taxes and profit from the work performed on monastery lands. In Derge, monasteries with powerful teachers were supported by the state.

在该宗教中存在叛教的概念吗：

— 否

Notes: Tibetan nonsectarianism, particularly as articulated by Kongtrul, was incredibly expansive, and included almost all Tibetan Buddhists. As with theories of liberal tolerance, nonsectarianism encountered theoretical difficulties in its own intolerance of intolerance, but there was no conception of apostasy in the sense for formally dispelling someone from the sangha on ideological grounds.

大小和结构

在样本区域中的宗教团体信奉者人数(估计人口，数字)

— 未知领域

Notes: The initial proponents of nonsectarianism were elite philosopher-monks who sought to induce a larger shift in the Tibetan understanding of the relationships among different Buddhist groups. In this sense, the number of people actively theorizing the concept was perhaps quite small, but their impact was significant and eventually felt throughout the Tibetan world. Because the nonsectarian writers were seeking to effect an intellectual shift and did not actively demarcate a movement, it is difficult to capture the extent of their influence in numerical terms.

样本区域中的宗教团体的信奉者数量(在样本区域人口中的百分比，数字)

— 未知领域

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经典

宗教团体有经典吗：

经典是一个统称，指的是受到尊崇、与其它文本相比被认为具有特别的权威性和神圣性的文本。严格意义上经典指书写的文本，但是也存在“口述经典”（比如印度的吠陀经典）。

— 是

Notes: The Tibetan Buddhist canon is divided into the Kagyur (bka' 'gyur), which nominally contains the words of the Buddha, and the Tengyur (bstan 'gyur), which contains later Indian commentaries, though in practice the division is not rigid. Both were compiled in approximately the fourteenth century, but neither body is closed or fixed. Although both bodies purport to contain Indian works, western historians treat many of the texts as authored or extensively revived by Tibetans. In addition to these two standardized bodies of scripture, many of the nineteenth-century authors who theorized nonsectarianism also accepted a body of scriptures specific to the Nyingma school of Tibetan Buddhism called the The Hundred-Thousand Nyingma Tantras (rnying ma rgyud 'bum). Most of these tantras were composed around the same time as those found in the Kagyur and Tengyur, and some tantras are found in both collections. The Nyingma Tantras represent less a systematic collection of specifically Nyingma tantras than an ad hoc compilation of scriptures rejected by other schools and hence excluded from the Kagyur and Tengyur, in part because many of the texts are treasure texts (gter ma) whose historical legitimacy is questioned by non-Nyingmapas.

↳ 它们是书面的吗：

— 是

Notes: Yes, the Kagyur, Tengyur, and Hundred-Thousand Nyingma Tantras all exist in textual form. Sponsoring a printing of the entire canon was considered an especially meritorious act for those with the financial means to do so, especially rulers. The royal family of Derge, whence many of the nonsectarian teachers hailed, was famous for the quality and tolerance of its printing press, and they sponsored important editions of all three canons of scriptures.

↳ 它们是口述的吗：

— 是

Notes: Although the scriptures mentioned above were all written, there were also tantric teachings that were transmitted primarily or exclusively in oral instructions. Many of the tantric texts included in the above canons could only be rendered intelligible when accompanied by the oral initiation or commentary of an initiated teacher, and as such read more like lecture-aides or shorthand than systematic treatises. This meant that to receive many Tibetan tantric teachings, one had to seek out an initiated teacher from whom to receive the teaching in addition to finding a relevant text.

↳ 经典的来源和一个（或一组）故事有关吗：

— 是

↳ 由至高无上的神揭示：

— 否

↳ 由其他超自然生灵揭示：

— 是

Notes: Although there is no single story for how these scriptures came to the Tibetan people, the Tibetan genre of "dharma history" (chos 'byung) is designed to illustrate the Indian origins of various Buddhist teachings and explain how they entered Tibet. Some teachings were simply transmitted in textual form from Sanskrit or other Indian languages into Tibet, but some were brought personally by Indian teachers and tantric masters who traveled to Tibet. The phrase "supernatural" is slightly problematic in Buddhism, but many of these tantric masters were able to kill demons, perform miracles, cast hailstorms, and do other actions beyond the capacities of ordinary people.

↳ 由至高无上的神启示：

— 否

↳ 由其他超自然生灵启示：

— 是

Notes: See above.

↳ 来源于神或半神半人：

— 是

Notes: If we treat the Buddha as a semi-divine being, then this is true, as all the Tibetan Buddhist teachings were said to be attributable to the Buddha himself, generally as a historical figure, but sometimes in other capacities, like teachings revealed in dreams or through Buddhahood as a principle.

↳ 来源于凡人：

— 否

Notes: Although historians treat many of the scriptures as human- and specifically Tibetan-authored, the tradition itself would claim that all scriptures were authored or inspired by enlightened beings.

↳ 这一经典是否是可以改变：

— 是

Notes: At the broadest level, the canons are not strictly closed, and their contents are constantly being renegotiated. Each printing of the Kagyur, Tengyur, and Hundred-Thousand Nyingma Tantras varies slightly in its contents. Individual texts are also gradually altered, sometimes intentionally and sometimes inadvertently, by scribes and editors across the centuries. Moreover, sometimes a scriptural commentary is written or revealed that will cast a

new light on the interpretation of a given scripture.

↳ 是否存在诠释经典的正式机构（比如被宗教团体或者政治领袖所授权的机构）：

— 是

Notes: Monastic institutions train monks (and, less often, nuns) in scriptural interpretation and performance. In Tibet, monastic institutions serve as one of the prime transmitters of secular and religious knowledge alike, as well as sites of great political power.

↳ 可以抛开这些机构来诠释经典吗：

— 是

Notes: Yes, lay religious practitioners also engage the scriptures and offer scriptural commentaries, particularly with respect to tantra. However, the monastic institutions broadly define scriptural orthodoxy.

↳ 只有被正式批准的人员才可以诠释经典：

— 否

Notes: No, laypeople can also interpret the scriptures. Tantric practice in particular is associated with antinomianism and anti-institutionalism.

↳ 是否存在一个专门被训练从事经典传布的特定群体：

— 是

Notes: Wealthy monasteries often employ scribes or their own printing press for this purpose. Sometimes wealthy donors or political leaders would sponsor the copying or printing of a large body of scriptures as a merit-generating practice. Individual practice and monastic lineages would also transmit their own oral commentaries or teachings by which to interpret the orthodox scriptures. One of the main goals of the nonsectarian teachers was the preservation of scriptures they feared were on the verge of extinction.

↳ 是否存在一部结集的典籍经藏：

— 是

Notes: See above. Yes, although this codification is somewhat less strict in Tibetan Buddhism than in many other religions. At the broadest level, the canons are not strictly closed, and their contents are constantly being renegotiated. Each printing of the Kagyur, Tengyur, and Hundred-Thousand Nyingma Tantras varies slightly in its contents. Some Tibetan thinkers have argued that there should at least be a theoretically identifiable canon of genuine scriptures, while others value the canons' flexibility.

建筑，地理

是否存在纪念性的宗教建筑物：

— 是

Notes: Tibet has a rich history of sacral architecture, including stupas, thangka paintings, prayer halls,

and statues of important deities or bodhisattvas.

↳ 在一般的定居地，所有宗教纪念性质建筑、纪念物面积所占百分比是多少：

— 我不知道

Notes: Perhaps it would be more accurate to say that it would depend on the settlement. Every Tibetan settlement would have at least some sort of shrine. In communities large enough to have a monastery, the monastery's prayer hall would likely be the largest building in the town. Although it is difficult to put a percentage on the total area occupied by such monuments, one might fairly say that religious monuments often function as the epicenter of Tibetan settlements.

↳ 最大的单体宗教纪念物、建筑的面积，以平方米计

— 未知领域

Notes: There are not in any large religious monuments that are associated with the nonsectarian tradition in particular.

↳ 最大的单体宗教纪念物、建筑的高度，以米计

— 未知领域

Notes: See above.

↳ 一般纪念物、建筑的尺寸，平方米

— 未知领域

Notes: See above

↳ 一般纪念建筑、纪念物的高度，米

— 未知领域

Notes: See above

↳ 在最大的定居地，所有宗教纪念物、纪念建筑总体面积所占区域百分比是多少？

— 未知领域

Notes: See above

有不同种类的宗教纪念性建筑物吗？

— 是

↳ 陵墓

— 是

Notes: Tibetan stupas often contain the relics or remains of a great lama in their center. Following a sky burial, the flesh and viscera of the deceased are fed to vultures, while the bones

are ground into a powder, mixed with tsampa barley, and placed at an auspicious site.

↳ 公墓

— 否

Notes: Tibetans are more likely to dispose of bodies through cremation or sky burial than through burial in the ground.

↳ 庙宇

— 是

Notes: Every monastery, including those occupied by the nonsectarian authors, would have had at least one temple, and most would have had far more.

↳ 圣坛

— 是

Notes: Shrines are common in eastern Tibet, particularly to deities who protect the local monastery, people, and land.

↳ 用于礼拜的标志性建筑

— 是

Notes: Even unoccupied areas of Tibet often include devotional markers, like prayer flags or shrines in remote mountain passes offered to the gods of the pass.

↳ 大规模集会点（庭院、广场等，用可见物或结构永久划分出来的场所）

— 是

Notes: Many Tibetan temples have a large square outside their entrance that might be the largest gathering place in the town. Although the square is often used in religious ceremonies, it might also be used for quasi-secular gatherings.

↳ 其它种类的宗教纪念性建筑物

— 是: Although stupas are tombs in a certain sense, they deserve mention as their own form of monumental architecture. The merit associated with the holy object inside transfers to practitioners who circumambulate the stupa, and stupas often serve as a social and religious center for Tibetan towns.

是否存在表征标志

— 是

↳ 表征在哪里显示【多选】

— 在人

— 在家里

—在所有公共场所

Notes: Images of Tibetan deities are found almost everywhere--on the walls of stupas, in shrines, on the outside of stupas, in family shrines, etc.--often to generate blessings and/or protection. Tibetans might also wear an amulet with iconography around their necks, hence the "on persons."

↳ 宗教团体的表征标志有明显特色吗

—否

Notes: Although Tibetan iconography broadly is quite distinct relative to other regions and forms of Buddhism, the nonsectarian masters themselves did not employ their own distinctive iconography.

是否有专门的地点用于神圣行活动或者被认为是神圣的：

—是

Notes: The nonsectarian masters, especially Jamgon Kongtrul and Chokgyur Lingpa, expended a great deal of time and resources sacralizing the land of eastern Tibet, both by writing pilgrimage guides and withdrawing termas (gter ma) like texts, statues, and medicinal pills that aid one in the journey to enlightenment and embedding eastern Tibet within a larger Buddhist cosmological framework.

↳ 神圣场地是否适应环境特点：

“环境特点”指的是风景、山水、罗盘方位等等的特征。

—是

Notes: Different deities are often associated with different environmental features and need to be propitiated. For instance, gods of mountain passes need to be propitiated to ensure safe passage, earthquakes and floods are often attributed to agitated nagas (klu). Certain sites will appear as ordinary landscapes to average beings, but as Buddha fields or other sacred sites to highly realized Buddhas and bodhisattvas.

有朝圣活动吗：

—是

Notes: Many of the nonsectarian masters spent large portions of their lives engaged in pilgrimage, sometimes to the traditionally holy sites of central Tibet, but also to sacred places in Eastern Tibet that the masters would reinscribe with new significance by revealing new treasures and treasure-texts hidden in their depths.

↳ 朝圣活动如何严格：

—可选择的（常见）

Notes: Most ordinary Tibetans as well as Buddhist masters would visit local pilgrimage sites. Although it was common to consult a pilgrimage guide written by a previous Buddhist master explaining the significance of the site and how to engage, pilgrimages were relatively informal and could vary according to the needs of individual pilgrims.

信仰

埋葬和来世

是否存在精神-肉体的区分

只有当人格（或意识）随肉体死亡而消亡时回答“否”。回答是并不一定意味着存在笛卡尔精神/肉体二元论，而只意味着人格（或意识）的一些要素在肉体死后尚存。

一是

Notes: In the sense that one exists in most Buddhist schools of thought; the nonsectarian teachers were not particularly distinctive on this point.

↳ 精神 - 心灵被认为具有异乎其它身体部位的能力或特质

一是

Notes: The wording of this question fails to capture Buddhist categories, but broadly speaking "consciousness" is considered theoretically isolatable from other parts of the body.

↳ 精神 - 心灵被认为是非物质的，在本体论上不同于身体

一是

Notes: In a very broad sense, yes. At some level one's karma and, in many Buddhist schools, consciousness, survive one's death while one's body does not.

↳ 其它心灵-身体关系：

一否

对来世的信仰：

一是

Notes: Following Buddhist orthodoxy, one is reincarnated according to the karmic effects of one's actions.

↳ 该宗教团体对来世的空间位置有具体描述吗

一是

Notes: There are six possible realms of Buddhist rebirth: God, demigod, human, animal, hungry ghost, and hell. The former three realms are generally considered positive rebirths insofar as they facilitate enlightened practice, while the latter three realms are generally considered negative rebirths insofar as they do not.

↳ 来世在这个世界之外的特定领域空间：

一是

Notes: Yes, for the god, demigod, and hell realms.

↳ 来世被模糊定义为“上面”的空间：

— 是

Notes: Yes, for the gods and demigods.

↳ 来世被模糊定义为“下面”的空间：

— 是

Notes: Yes, for the hell realms.

↳ 来世被模糊定义为某个平行空间：

— 是

Notes: For humans, animals, and hungry ghosts.

↳ 来世在“其他”空间：

— 是: Certain enlightened or quasi-enlightened beings are said to be able to transcend these six realms altogether, although the understanding of their ontological status varies widely within Buddhism.

在这个世界上的转世

— 是

Notes: It depends how broadly "world" is conceived, but rebirth takes place within the present universe. In certain cases, one might be reborn into the very community in which one lived one's previous life.

↳ 以人形转世：

— 是

↳ 以动物／植物的形态转世：

— 是

Notes: More often as an animal. Plants are generally considered sentient within Buddhist cosmologies, but their relationship to the six realms of rebirths varies widely.

↳ 以非生物的形态转世：

— 否

Notes: The Buddhist cosmology distinguishes "sentient beings" to whom one has an ethical obligation from inanimate objects, to which one does not. However, in certain Tibetan practices one might transfer one's consciousness into an inanimate object. Similarly, objects like "ground" or "mountain" that are generally not considered sentient in Euro-American cosmologies might have this sense in Tibetan ones.

↳ 以非个体的形态转世（比如集体重生、部落、家族等等）：

— 否

Notes: If I am understanding the sense of the question correctly, then no. However, tulkus (sprul sku) are able to control their own emanations and rebirths and so often incarnate in lineages. For instance, the famous Dalai Lama lineage is sometimes understood as representing fourteen distinct births of a single being, the bodhisattva of compassion Avalokiteśvara (sphyan ras gzigs).

↳ 和超越此生的因果机制有联系（比如，业力）：

— 是

Notes: The Tibetan understanding of rebirth is linked directly to one's karma.

↳ 这个世界中的其他形式的转世

— 否

对信众的遗体有特别处置吗：

— 是

Notes: The bodies of highly realized masters were often said not to decay at the same rate or at all after their death. Many remained in a meditative posture even after dying. Portions of the corpse were often used as relics, often by preservation in a stupa that could then be circumambulated for karmic benefit. Similarly, the death of great teachers was often accompanied by great signs, for instance flowers coming from the sky, pleasant smells wafting through the air, or the sound of music.

↳ 火化

— 是

Notes: Access to timber and fuel was somewhat easier than in central Tibet, and so cremation was a relatively common form of burial.

↳ 制成木乃伊

— 否

Notes: Although the bodies of some great masters were said not to decay of their power.

↳ 埋葬：

— 是

Notes: The bodies of some great masters were placed into coffins and held in the monastery. However, this was significantly less common than cremation and sky burials.

↳ 遗体被蜷屈（腿部弯曲或身体蜷缩）

— 否

↳ 遗体被伸展（或躺或卧）

— 是

↳ 遗体竖立（遗体以站姿安葬）：
— 否

↳ 遗体以其他方式安葬：
— 否

↳ 被食用：
— 否

↳ 暴露放置（比如风干）：
— 否

↳ 喂动物：
— 是

Notes: Corpses were often fed to vultures in a practice known as a "sky burial." The remaining bones would then be ground into a paste mixed with the Tibetan barley tsampa and taken to an auspicious site.

↳ 二次埋葬：
— 是

Notes: Sometimes the relics of a master would be moved from one holy site to another, but secondary burial was not a standardized ritual.

↳ 遗体再处理：
— 否

↳ 其他强化（就时间或资源的耗费而言）处理方法 [请注明]
— 否

埋葬过程中或者墓穴中是否存在一起殉葬现象
— 否

是否存在陪葬品：
— 我不知道

有正式的葬礼吗：
— 是

Notes: The funerals of great teachers were a significant communal event and required days of rituals celebrating their life and ensuring a good rebirth.

↳ 树立纪念碑：

— 否

↳ 葬于公墓：

— 否

↳ 葬于家庭墓地或教堂地下室

— 否

↳ 在家里（埋在房屋地下或者在有正常家庭活动的地方）

— 否

↳ 其他正式的葬礼形式：

— 是: Sky-burial or cremation, see above.

超自然存在

有超自然存在吗：

— 是

Notes: The gods play an important role in Tibetan Buddhism in a variety of areas. Deities of the landscape must be propitiated in order for society to function smoothly. Gods also can be propitiated to help individuals--e.g. with illness, fertility, economic success, etc. Deities also guide one through complex meditations that can lead to enlightenment; much of the nonsectarian project was concerned with restoring rituals that were feared to be on the cusp of extinction, and elevating deities local to Eastern Tibet at the expense of the orthodox ones promoted by Central Tibetan institutions.

↳ 有一个至上之神存在

— 否

Notes: Not in the sense of a monotheistic god who is ontologically distinct from its creation.

↳ 过去人的灵魂是存在的：

— 是

Notes: According to Buddhist cosmology, every being has been trapped in samsara for such a long period of time that all beings, including gods, have previously taken rebirth in every realm, including that of humans. However, this dimension of the gods is not stressed in everyday life.

↳ 人类灵魂可以被看到

— 否

↳ 人类灵魂可以用身体感触到：

— 否

↳ 过去人的灵魂对这个世界有所认知：

— 是

↳ 人类灵魂的所知限于特定领域的人类事务：

— 否

↳ 人类灵魂的所知限于采样地区的（一个或多个）特定区域：

— 否

Notes: The gods are, if not fully omniscient, at least functionally omniscient with respect to human affairs. However, some gods might be concerned primarily with the affairs of the area in which they reside, particularly when they are linked to a particular geographical area or feature, like a mountain pass.

↳ 人类灵魂对采样地区无所不知：

— 是

↳ 人类灵魂对采样地区以外无所不知：

— 是

↳ 不论你（在公共场所）置身何处，人类灵魂都可以看到你：

— 是

↳ 不论置身何处，人类灵魂都可以看到你（比如在黑暗中和家里）：

— 是

↳ 人类灵魂可以看穿你的心/脑（隐秘的动机）：

— 是

Notes: This makes the gods and spirits particularly useful as meditation guides.

↳ 人类灵魂知道你的基本特征个性（个人本质）：

— 是

Notes: In Buddhism there is no essence to know, but many can see your karmic stream.

↳ 人类灵魂知道你将来的人生际遇/你将会做什么（预测未来的能力）：
— 否

↳ 人类灵魂关于这个世界有其他种类的知识：
— 否

↳ 人类灵魂至上对这个世界能够有意施发因果效力：
— 是

Notes: This is precisely why they are valuable to propitiate. The gods can both reward and punish according to whether they are appeased or offended.

↳ 人类灵魂可以奖赏：
— 是

↳ 人类灵魂可以惩罚：
— 是

↳ 人类灵魂对这个世界有间接因果效应：
— 是

↳ 人类灵魂对人生有记忆：
— 是

Notes: As mentioned in the broader answer above, although the gods were technically humans in a former life, this aspect of their experience is rarely emphasized.

↳ 人类灵魂展现出积极的情感：
— 是

↳ 人类灵魂展现出负面的情感：
— 是

Notes: Buddhist deities often have both a compassionate and a wrathful form, so that even the wrathful form is working to oppose the foes of the dharma and is not intrinsically wrathful. However, non-Buddhist deities might be malicious in their own right and work to thwart human flourishing.

↳ 人类灵魂有饥饿感：

— 是

Notes: Gods do not generally possess hunger, although they can be propitiated through food offerings. Hungry ghosts, however, are defined by their hunger, condemned to wander the earth perpetually hungry.

↳ 人类灵魂有/展现出一些其他特征：

— 否

↳ 人类灵魂和生灵沟通：

— 是

Notes: Especially when given offerings or otherwise propitiated.

↳ 在清醒状态下的日常生活中：

— 否

Notes: This would not be common except for especially realized beings.

↳ 在睡梦中：

— 是

Notes: This was quite common for the nonsectarian masters. Many of the teachings that Kongtrul and others "recovered" were in fact bestowed by deities in dreams in order to fill gaps in transmission lines.

↳ 在被附体催眠状态中：

— 是

Notes: Tibetan oracles and shamans commonly fall into a trance before receiving a divination. In general this is a specialized function associated with a particular office, but ordinary beings might on occasion also fall into such a trance state.

↳ 通过占卜行为：

— 是

Notes: See above

↳ 只通过专业的宗教人士：

— 否

Notes: But primarily through specialists; see above.

↳ 只通过君主：

— 否

↳ 其他与生灵的交流方式：

—是: Although Tibetan deities could communicate with the living through a variety of means, meditation is one worth stressing. Tantric practices and meditations in particular were often tailored toward a particular deity, such that the deity in question would grant the practitioner special insights or powers.

↳ 有非人类的超自然存在：

— 是

Notes: See the discussion of the Buddhist realms above. The other realms of rebirth are not strictly supernatural, but they do refer to ways of being other than the human.

↳ 这些超自然存在可以被看到：

— 是

Notes: It is interesting to consider whether "animals" would count as a supernatural being in this context, insofar as they are a part of daily human experience but occupy a radically different form of being.

↳ 这些超自然存在可以用身体感触到：

— 是

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界有认知：

— 是

↳ 非人类的超自然存在的所知限于特定的领域人类事务：

— 否

↳ 非人类的超自然存在的所知限于采样地区的（一个或多个）特定区域：

— 否

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对采样地区内无所不知：

— 是

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对采样地区以外无所不知：

— 是

- ↳ 不论你（在公共场所）置身何处，非人类的超自然存在都可以看到你：
 - 是
- ↳ 不论你置身何处非人类的超自然存在都可以看到你（比如在黑暗中和家里）：
 - 是
- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在可以看穿你的心/脑中（隐秘的动机）：
 - 是
- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在知道你的基本特征个性（个人本质）：
 - 是
- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在知道你将来的人生际遇/你将会做什么（预测未来的能力）：
 - 是
- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界有其他的认知：
 - 否
- ↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界可以有意施发因果效应：
 - 是
- ↳ 这些超自然存在可以奖赏：
 - 是
- ↳ 这些超自然存在可以惩罚：
 - 是
- ↳ 这些超自然存在对这个世界有间接的因果效应：
 - 是
- ↳ 这些超自然存在展现出积极的情感：
 - 是
- ↳ 这些超自然存在展现出负面的情感：
 - 是

↳ 这些超自然存在有饥饿感：

— 是

↳ 这些超自然存在有/展现出一些其他特征：

— 否

↳ 有半人半神的存在：

— 是

Notes: This is an interesting way of describing important lamas or tulkus who are often understood as bodhisattvas who have taken rebirth in the human realm to work for the benefit of humanity or a specific community.

↳ 这些半人半神的存在可以被看到：

— 是

↳ 这些半人半神的存在可以用肢体感触到：

— 是

↳ 半人半神的存在对这个世界有所认知：

— 是

Notes: The capacities will vary according to the individual teacher or lama. Sometimes a teacher might be popularly understood as fully omniscient, while others might be seen as simply having greater spiritual insight than ordinary beings. Some might be especially skilled at one divine aspect like healing or divination but lack others.

↳ 半人半神的存在所知限于特定领域的人类事务：

— 否

↳ 半人半神的存在所知限于采样地区的（一个或多个）特定区域：

— 否

↳ 半人半神的存在对于采样地区内无所不知：

— 是

↳ 半人半神的存在对于采样地区以外无所不知：

— 是

↳ 不论你（在公共场所）置身何处，半人半神的存在可以看到你：

—是

↳ 不论你置身何处半人半神的存在都看到你（比如在黑暗中和家里）：

—否

↳ 半人半神的存在可以看穿你的心/脑中（隐秘的动机）：

—是

Notes: Many important lamas are understood to have this capacity.

↳ 半人半神的存在知道你的基本特征个性（个人特质）：

—是

↳ 半人半神的存在知道你将来的人生际遇/你将会做什么（预测未来的能力）：

—否

Notes: Although many lamas are able to prophesy and foretell future events, they are not necessarily determinative.

↳ 半人半神对人事件有其它认知：

—是: Particularly the ability to understand karmic interconnections.

↳ 半人半神的存在对于这个世界有意造成因果效应：

—是

↳ 这些半人半神的存在可以奖赏：

—是

↳ 这些半人半神的存在可以惩罚：

—是

↳ 这些半人半神的存在对这个世界上有间接因果效应：

—是

↳ 这些半人半神的存在展现出积极的情感：

—是

↳ 这些半人半神的存在展现出负面的情感：

—是

↳ 这些半人半神的存在有饥饿感：

— 是

↳ 这些半人半神的存在有/展现出一些其他特征：

— 否

↳ 这些半人半神的存在和生灵沟通

— 是

↳ 在清醒状态下的日常生活中：

— 是

Notes: One might dream of a lama or consult one for a divination, however, unlike gods and deities, lamas and tulkus are experienced as everyday individuals.

↳ 在睡梦中：

— 是

↳ 在被附体催眠状态中：

— 否

↳ 通过占卜行为：

— 否

Notes: In general the lama would be the one performing the divination rather than the one summoned.

↳ 只通过宗教专业人员：

— 否

↳ 只通过君主：

— 否

↳ 其他与生灵的交流方式：

— 否

↳ 宗教团体具有多种超自然存在：

— 是

Notes: See discussion of realms above.

↳ 以基于家庭模式的亲属关系编排：

— 是

Notes: Some of the different classes of deities are categorized according to which "Buddha family" they belong to.

↳ 按照高下阶层编排：

— 是

Notes: Not strictly, but some deities are considered broadly more significant than others.

↳ 各自的权力是限于所属领域的：

— 否

Notes: Not generally, although some deities are associated with specific geographies.

↳ 万神庙的其他组织方式：

— 否

超自然监督

是否存在超自然的监视：

“超自然监视”是指超自然存在监视人类的行为以及或者思想，特别是涉及到社会准则或潜在性违规的情况。

— 是

Notes: Perhaps the most obvious example of this would be Yama (Gshin rje), the personification of karma who judges a being according to their karma and determines their rebirth. However, one can also offend local deities by violating their sovereignty or acting unethically.

↳ 有针对遵守亲社会规范的超自然监视：

亲社会规范是指增加族群中成员协作的规范，包括明显的“道德”或“伦理”规范，也延伸至关于履行合约与誓言，提供热情款待，在紧急情况下互相帮助等等。

— 是

Notes: Broadly speaking yes insofar as prosocial behavior is often correlated with good karma.

↳ 超自然存在在意禁忌：

— 是

↳ 食物：

— 是

Notes: This is true both at an individual level (e.g. certain foods should be offered or set aside for the gods) and a social one (e.g. certain fields should only be planted at certain times or after they have been blessed).

↳ 神圣空间：

一是

Notes: In many temples one should not wear shoes, gaze upon protector deities, and so forth. Others are gender segregated and only men are permitted inside.

↳ 神圣物品

一是

Notes: There are a number of sacred ritual objects in Tibetan rituals, including bells, vajras (rdo rje), drums, conch shells that are often used as instruments, among many others.

↳ 超自然存在在意其他事项：

一是: They are at least aware of one another and can often be pitted against one another. Buddhist deities often work in complimentary ways to benefit practitioners.

↳ 超自然存在关切教友之间的杀害：

一是

Notes: One of the primary goals of the nonsectarian movement was to convince Central Tibetan Buddhists and government authorities that the practitioners of different lineages of Tibetan Buddhism were in fact coreligionists. The fear that the Gelug, the school of Tibetan Buddhism associated with Lhasa hegemony, would persecute or suppress the other schools was at the heart of the nonsectarian project.

↳ 超自然存在关切其他宗教的信徒的谋杀：

一是

Notes: However, one justification for war was protecting the dharma, which implicitly distinguishes between an in- and out-group.

↳ 超自然存在关切其它政权成员的谋杀：

一是

Notes: See above.

↳ 超自然存在关注性行为：

一是

↳ 通奸：

— 是

Notes: However, there were some circumstances in which adultery was ethically and socially permissible.

↳ 乱伦：

— 是

Notes: Expressly prohibited within one's immediate family.

↳ 其他性行为：

— 是: Tantric sexual practices are incredibly complex and would require their own article to explain in a nuanced way. It suffices to say here that there were certain well-defined ritual contexts, a Buddhist master could have sex with a practitioner for the express purpose of generating merit or insight for the master, rather than out of sexual desire.

↳ 超自然存在在意撒谎行为：

— 是

↳ 超自然存在在意誓言的执行：

— 是

Notes: Violating one's bodhisattva and/or tantric vows were seen as especially egregious and would incur divine or karmic retribution.

↳ 超自然存在在意懒惰：

— 我不知道

Notes: I can't remember seeing this expressly prohibited, and there are many stories of tantric masters who pretend not to work. Emily Yeh has written extensively on the function of discourses of laziness among contemporary Tibetans, but I don't remember seeing this discussed in nineteenth-century discourse.

Reference: Yeh, Emily T.. *Taming Tibet: Landscape Transformation and the Gift of Chinese Development*.. Cornell University Press, 2013.

↳ 超自然存在在意巫术：

— 是

Notes: Tibetan tantric masters were capable of casting hailstorms, killing from a distance, and causing crops to wither, among other actions. Similarly, the nonsectarian masters were often summoned by rulers to exorcise demons, restore rain, and perform other sorcerous rituals.

↳ 超自然存在在意非致命的打斗：

— 是

Notes: One could receive karmic punishment for violence and wrath.

↳ 超自然存在注意规避风险：

— 我不知道

Notes: Not that I remember but I'd hesitate to say categorically no.

↳ 超自然存在在意对长者的不敬：

— 是

↳ 超自然存在在乎说长道短的行为：

— 是

↳ 超自然存在在意财产犯罪：

— 我不知道

Notes: I can't remember a case of a god or deity intervening because of a property crime, but often property crimes are the impetus for conflicts in which divine beings become involved.

↳ 超自然存在在乎对仪礼的正确奉守：

— 是

Notes: Proper ritual observance is at the heart of much Tibetan Buddhist practice, both for states who wish to be prosperous and safe, and for individuals with religious goals. Kongtrul was known for being an especially fastidious and efficacious ritual-master. Much of the nonsectarian project was devoted to reviving ritual practices that the teachers feared were on the cusp of extinction.

↳ 超自然存在在乎仪式的演绎：

— 是

Notes: See above.

↳ 超自然存在在意度化无宗教信仰者：

— 是

Notes: At least in theory, as there are numerous stories of gods and tantric masters doing battle with demons to make safe the spread of Buddhism across Tibet. In practice, the Tibetans did not devote considerable resources to converting non-Buddhists to Buddhism. The various schools of Tibetan Buddhism often engaged in polemical debate and saw one another as competitors or illegitimate. The nonsectarian masters hoped to ensure some measure of political and religious tolerance even as they allowed for the possibility of hierarchies of Buddhist practice and philosophy.

↳ 超自然存在在意经济上的公平：

— 否

Notes: Not in the sense of economic equality. However, there was a broad conception that the rich and powerful had earned their station through previous karmic achievements.

↳ 超自然存在在意个人卫生：

— 否

Notes: Tantric masters would often appear in the guise of filthy beggars or ascetics to underscore the lack of connection between enlightened practice and social status. In that sense they might be said to care about it, but not to value it.

↳ 超自然存在在意其他事物：

— 是: They are aware of one another; the Buddhist deities share a commitment to spreading and protecting the dharma, while non-Buddhist spirits and deities often have their own agendas.

超自然存在施加惩罚吗：

— 是

Notes: Karmic theory in Buddhism is complex, and some might argue that karma is not powered by divine action, even though this process is often depicted anthropomorphically. However, in Tibet, even local deities would often punish those who challenged their sovereignty, for instance, demons who occupied geographical features.

↳ 超自然惩罚的来源或是动因是已知的吗：

— 是

Notes: One of the responsibilities of the ritual specialist is to determine the cause of a negative outcome, for instance one's previous negative karma, drawing a god's ire, etc.

↳ 只由至上之神完成

— 否

↳ 由许多超自然存在完成：

— 是

↳ 由客观的因果定律来完成：

— 是

Notes: Karma, although not exclusively.

↳ 由其他实体或其他方式完成【请注明】：

— 否

↳ 超自然惩罚的存在原因是已知的吗：

— 是

Notes: See above.

↳ 为了实现宗教的仪式-崇拜的信奉：

— 是

↳ 为了强制实施团体准则：

— 是

Notes: Perhaps from a sociological perspective, although I am less sure from a religious one.

↳ 为了阻止自私自利：

— 是

↳ 随机：

— 否

Notes: It is key to Buddhist cosmology that these acts are not random, but can be determined and corrected through proper action.

↳ 其它【请注明】

— 否

↳ 超自然惩罚在来世施行：

— 是

↳ 宗教团体非常强调来世的超自然惩罚：

— 是

↳ 来世的惩罚包括轻微的感觉不悦：

— 是

Notes: Perhaps in the form of rebirth as an animal, although this is not stressed.

↳ 来世的惩罚包括极度的感觉的不悦：

— 是

Notes: E.g. in the form of rebirth in a hell realm, as a hungry ghost, or in some animal forms.

↳ 来世的惩罚包括转世成为低等生命形式：

— 是

Notes: See above.

↳ 来世的惩罚包括转世到低级领域：

— 是

Notes: See above.

↳ 其它【请注明】

— 否

↳ 超自然惩罚在今世施行：

— 是

Notes: Karma informs not only one's rebirth, but every aspect of one's life.

↳ 宗教团体非常强调今世的超自然惩罚：

— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括噩运：

— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括政治上的失败：

— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括在战斗中失败：

— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括农作物欠收或恶劣天气：

— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括出游上灾祸：

— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括轻微的不悦：

— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括强烈的不悦：

— 是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括疾病：

—是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括生育上出问题：

—是

↳ 今世的惩罚包括后代承受噩运：

—是

↳ 其它【请注明】

—是

Notes: Karma informs all aspects of one's life and can lead to any reward or punishment.

超自然存在赐予奖赏吗：

—是

↳ 超自然奖赏的来源/目的是已知的吗：

—是

Notes: Same as for above; discerning the purpose and nature of rewards is the job of the ritual specialist.

↳ 只由至高的神完成：

—否

↳ 由许多超自然存在完成：

—是

↳ 由客观的因果定律完成：

—是

Notes: Karma.

↳ 为了实现宗教的仪式-崇拜的信奉：

—是

↳ 为了推行团体规范：

—是

Notes: From a sociological perspective, although perhaps not from a religious one.

↳ 为了阻止自私自利：
— 是

↳ 随机：
— 否

↳ 在来世赐予超自然奖赏：
— 是

↳ 宗教团体非常强调来世的超自然奖赏：
— 是

↳ 来世的奖赏包括轻微的感官愉悦：
— 是

↳ 来世的奖赏包括极度的感官愉悦：
— 是

↳ 来世的奖赏包括永恒的幸福：
— 否

Notes: Even gods in Buddhism are eventually subject to death and impermanence.

↳ 来世的奖赏包括转世为更高级生命形式：
— 是

Notes: As a god, demigod, or human

↳ 来世的奖赏包括投生到更高级的领域中：
— 是

Notes: See above

↳ 其它【请注明】：
— 是

Notes: Karma influences all aspects of one's life.

↳ 在今世赐予超自然奖赏：
— 是

↳ 宗教团体非常强调今世的超自然奖赏：
—是

↳ 今世的奖赏包括好运：
—是

↳ 今世的奖赏包括政治上的成功或权力：
—是

↳ 今世的奖赏包括在战斗的胜利：
—是

↳ 今世的奖赏包括和平或社会稳定：
—是

↳ 今世的奖赏包括好的收成或风调雨顺：
—是

↳ 今世的奖赏包括出行上一路顺风：
—是

↳ 今世的奖赏包括轻微的感觉愉悦：
—是

↳ 今世的奖赏包括极度的感觉愉悦：
—是

↳ 今世的奖赏包括更好的健康：
—是

↳ 今世的奖赏包括多子多孙：
—是

↳ 今世的奖赏包括子孙多福
—是

↳ 其它【请注明】

— 是

Notes: Karma informs all aspects of one's life.

救世主/末世论

是否存在救世主信仰：

— 是

Notes: Many of the nonsectarian masters believe that after a period of darkness during which the Buddhist teachings have entirely disappeared, the future Buddha Maitreya (Byams pa) will come to reintroduce the dharma to humans once again.

↳ 是否存在救世主的下落或者得知的时间？

— 是

↳ 已降生，可被识别：

— 否

↳ 将在现世降临：

— 否

↳ 会在特定的日期来临：

— 否

↳ 会在不久的将来来临，日期不确定：

— 否

↳ 会在遥远的将来来临，日期不确定：

— 是

Notes: After the dharma has disappeared from the world.

↳ 已经出现了：

— 否

↳ 从过去到未来众多救世主中的一个：

— 是

Notes: In the Tibetan and Mahayana conception, Maitreya is one in a long line of past and future Buddhas charged with a similar mission.

↳ 救世主的目的是已知的吗：

— 是

Notes: Maitreya will restore the Buddhist teachings to the world.

↳ 救世主是匡复政治统治的政治人物：

— 否

Notes: There will be political effects of Maitreya's coming, but this aspect is less stressed than the religious restoration he will inspire.

↳ 救世主是匡复宗教团体的神职人员：

— 是

↳ 其它目的：

— 否

规范与道德现实

该宗教团体规定总体性的社会准则了吗：

— 是

Notes: The primary intervention that the nonsectarian teachers wished to make was for all the Buddhist paths and schools to be understood as intrinsically valuable. In this sense, the group hoped to establish greater mutual respect and diminish inter-sectarian conflict.

该宗教团体存在传统和道德范畴的区分吗：

— 是

Notes: Most Buddhists, Mahayana Buddhists in particular, draw a distinction between ultimate and conventional reality. Conventional reality refers to the world as experienced by ordinary beings, wherein ordinary moral norms would hold. Ultimate reality refers to the world as experienced by enlightened beings, where ethics and moral norms have in some sense been transcended altogether. Many seemingly anti-moral or anti-social tantric practices--e.g. Buddhist masters who are alcoholics, have illicit sex, murder, etc.--are intended to undercut one's intuitive attachment to conventional morality.

↳ 这种区别的性质是什么：

— 强烈存在并强调

↳ 宗教团体对道德规范有专门规定吗：

— 是

Notes: These moral norms comprise the Buddhist teachings. The most relevant for the nonsectarian teachers is that enlightened beings do not discriminate among the superficially different Buddhist paths the way that ordinary beings do. In this sense, the conceptual

differences between the paths belong to conventional reality but not to ultimate reality, at least according to one understanding of nonsectarianism.

↳ 专门的道德规范和模糊的形而上学的观念模糊有不明显的联系：

— 是

↳ 专门的道德规范和模糊的形而上学的实体有明显的联系：

— 是

↳ 专门的道德规范和客观的宇宙秩序的有联系（比如业力）：

— 是

Notes: To karma.

↳ 专门的道德规范以某种方式和人形的存在相联系：

— 是

Notes: Assuming the Buddhist deities qualify as anthropomorphic beings.

↳ 专门的道德规范和人形化的存在的命令有明显的联系：

— 否

↳ 专门的道德规范和形而上的没有特别联系：

— 否

↳ 道德规范适用于：

— 社会里的所有人（除了奴隶、外侨）

Notes: This is an interesting query. Most ordinary Tibetans would be expected to follow only conventional morality, i.e. generating good karma in hopes of securing a good rebirth. However, much of the nonsectarian discourses is aimed at convincing elites of the soteriological value of a variety of esoteric practices and philosophical positions. Because the conventional/ultimate divide is emphasized quite broadly, I have interpreted it as broadly as possible in the checklist above, even though it was an open question whether women, non-elites, and others were capable of realizing such norms. The moral norms are said to hold universally, i.e. for all individuals, but non-Buddhists would not have been viewed as capable of fulfilling these moral norms.

常规

会员费用和惯例

该宗教团体要求成员禁欲(完全禁绝性生活)吗：

— 否

Notes: Although many of the nonsectarian teachers were monks, some were lay practitioners, and even some of the elite monks took consorts in their tantric practice.

该宗教团体要求成员节制性行为(部分禁止性生活)吗：

— 是

Notes: Even monks who engaged in sexual yoga were not permitted to have unconstrained sex.

↳ 一夫一妻制 (男性)：
— 否

↳ 一夫一妻制 (女性)：
— 否

↳ 其他性行为的限制 (男性)：
— 否

↳ 其他性行为的限制 (女性)：
— 否

该宗教团体要求成员阉割吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员斋戒吗：

— 否

Notes: However, individual members might practice as part of their religious practice.

该宗教团体要求成员断除某些食物 (对想吃的食物的禁忌) 吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员在身体上留下永久性疤痕或作疼痛的修整吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员忍受疼痛的身体姿势或暂时性的伤口吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成年成员的牺牲生命吗

“成年”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义中的超过18周岁的并且为他/她的行为负法律责任的人类，那么请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

— 否

该宗教团体要求儿童成员的牺牲吗

“儿童”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义，请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员自我牺牲（自杀）吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员贡献出财产／昂贵的物品吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员奉献出自己的时间吗（例如参加会议或仪式，常规祷告等）：

— 否

Notes: Although this might be true in practice, there was no strict requirement.

该宗教团体要求成员承受身体上的风险吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员接受道德戒律吗：

— 是

Notes: Although many of the teachers involved in the nonsectarian zeitgeist were monks and so adhered to monastic precepts, some were not. Definitionally, the discourse requires a recognition of religious tolerance and pluralism, and so in this sense one might speak of an ethical requirement.

成为该宗教团体的成员会被组外成员边缘化吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员参与小规模宗教仪式（私人的，家庭的）吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员参与大规模的宗教仪式吗：

比如，涉及两个或以上的家庭；包括有大规模的“典礼”和“节庆”。

— 否

Notes: Although in practice such participation was common, for example in funerary rituals and public *terma* revelations.

除了仪式之外还有群内的的标示性符号吗：

比如，关于外表的特别改变，比如割礼、纹身、牺牲等等。

— 否

Notes: After looking at the list of possible markers under "yes," I've opted for "no." However, all shared a discursive commitment to a nonsectarian orientation.

团体使用虚拟的亲族称谓吗：

— 是

Notes: Insofar as monastic groups treat the sangha as a family.

虚拟的亲族称谓是普遍的：

— 是

Notes: See above.

虚拟的亲族称谓是广泛的：

— 是

使用虚拟的亲族称谓，但不常见：

— 否

社会与机构

社会复杂程度

对宗教团体所属社会最恰当的描述为（请选其一）：

— 其他【请在评论中注明】

Notes: The different contributors to the formation of a nonsectarian zeitgeist lived across different polities. For example, those in Derge lived in a small kingdom that was sometimes claimed by the Qing, sometimes by Lhasa, but was able to maintain its own political autonomy. Much of eastern Tibet was conquered by the warrior Gonpo Namgyal in the mid nineteenth century; during these periods teachers would have lived in a very decentralized chiefdom. Others would have lived in areas that nominally paid fealty to the Qing or Lhasa, but would have been governed by the local monastery in day-to-day affairs. In this sense, although the different nonsectarian teachers can all meaningfully be described as Tibetan, their political situations were quite distinct.

福利

该宗教团体提供制度化的救助饥荒的服务吗：

— 是

Notes: Insofar as monasteries kept grain reserves for lean times.

饥荒救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 是

Notes: Through the state for Tibetans who lived in area with a centralized government, although the state's and monastery's reserves would have been coordinated.

该宗教团体提供制度化的的贫困救济吗：

— 是

Notes: This is an interesting query. Monastic institutions were a key economic cog in the societies in which they were embedded. As large landowners they provided the means of sustenance for large numbers of Tibetans, while the monasteries themselves derived a substantial income on the basis of that labor.

贫困救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 是

Notes: Through the state in areas with a strong centralized government.

该宗教团体对年老体弱者有制度化的关怀吗：

— 否

Notes: Although individual elderly monks and nuns were cared for within the monastery and on occasion elderly relatives might have come to live with important lamas (e.g. Jamgon Kongtrul's mother), this care was generally not institutionalized as far as I am aware.

对年老体弱者制度化的关怀是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 否

Notes: The elderly and infirm were generally cared for within individual families.

教育

该宗教团体为信众提供正规教育吗：

— 是

Notes: Tibetan monastic institutions became the site of much religious knowledge in Tibet, but also to what might be called secular knowledge. For instance, monasteries were not only the place one might train to become a Buddhist ritual master, but also a medical doctor, a painter, an engineer, etc. This education was not confined exclusively to monasteries--one might also apprentice with a master, but most Tibetan knowledge systems intersected with Buddhism in some fashion.

↳ 正规教育仅限于宗教专职人员吗：

— 否

Notes: While definitely oriented toward monks and nuns, it was at least in principle available to others. For instance, many important politicians and laypeople would come to the monastery to receive teachings and even go on retreat with many of the nonsectarian teachers.

↳ 男性和女性都能得到这种教育吗：

— 是

Notes: However, the education received by men and women was strikingly different. Although individual Tibetan women were able to become learned or great Buddhist teachers, monasteries and nunneries were categorically different institutions. The entire range of Tibetan knowledge was available to men, but women were often not taught esoteric tantric practices and philosophy on grounds that they lacked the capacity to realize their benefits.

正规教育是通过宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

— 是

Notes: Particularly through local apprenticeships, sometimes through state institutions. However, monasteries were undoubtedly the primary site of learning in Tibet.

↳ 男性和女性都能得到宗教团体以外的教育吗：

— 是

Notes: However, the same biases that informed monastic education informed extra-religious education as well.

官僚机构

团体的信徒与团体内的官方机构有互动吗？

— 否

Notes: This is an interesting query, one that of course hinges on the definition of formal bureaucracy. Although most monasteries, the nonsectarian teachers included, kept meticulous records, including catalogs of libraries, inventories of sacred objects, and receipts of payments and services, I don't believe this bureaucracy was formalized.

宗教信众与其他官僚机构有互动吗：

— 是

Notes: Eastern Tibetan institutions interacted with both the Lhasa and Qing governments, both of which had more formalized bureaucratic systems, particularly in the case of the Qing. The Derge royal family, for instance, exchanged titles with the Qing, which led to the Qing to consider Derge part of their empire, even as the gesture was not interpreted by the Derge royal family in the same way. In this sense, we might say that eastern Tibet was brought into a formal bureaucratic apparatus for the first time during the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries.

公共工程

该宗教团体储备公共食品吗：

— 是

Notes: Or at least stores food that can be distributed when necessary.

公共食品储备是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

一是

Notes: By the state as well, insofar as these can be distinguished in Tibet.

该宗教团体提供水资源管理（灌溉、防洪）吗：

一是

Notes: Insofar as the monasteries are also land owners and must irrigate the fields close to them. Irrigation and flood control also falls under the monastery's ritual purview.

水资源管理是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

一是

Notes: By the state as well, insofar as these can be distinguished in Tibet.

该宗教团体提供基础交通设施吗：

一是

Notes: Especially building roads that connected the monastery with nearby towns and trade routes.

基础交通设施是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

一是

Notes: By the state as well, insofar as these can be distinguished in Tibet.

纳税

该宗教团体课取税款或什一税吗：

一是

Notes: Monasteries were generally permitted to tax the areas within their jurisdiction and to benefit from the labor performed on monastery-owned lands. The various tax relationships between the state and the monastery were complex and varied across time and region; sometimes the two were synonymous, sometimes one had to pay taxes to both groups, sometimes the state would allow the monastery exclusively to receive the taxes of a given region as a boon of gratitude.

团体信众的税是由该宗教团体以外的机构来征收吗：

一是

Notes: By the state as well, insofar as these can be distinguished in Tibet. Although monks would have generally been exempt from these taxes, the monastery as a whole might have had to pay taxes on certain occasions, and non-monastics would have been subject to taxes from both groups.

强制

该宗教团体设有体制化的警务部门吗：

— 否

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的警务部门有互动吗：

— 是

Notes: Insofar as the local rulers had militias or armies that could be formed when the need arose.

该宗教团体设置体制化的法官吗：

— 否

Notes: Monasteries often adjudicated disputes and served as a de facto judicial system, but this process was generally not formalized or institutionalized, even if particular teachers became revered for their wisdom in settling such disputes.

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的司法系统有互动吗：

— 是

Notes: Often the state would also have some sort of judicial apparatus, but in practice monasteries settled many disputes.

该宗教团体施加制度化的处罚吗：

— 否

Notes: Although the adjudicator of a dispute could prescribe a punishment, the monastery would generally not directly enforce it, say through a military or police force.

宗教团体的信众承受宗教团体以外的体制下的处罚吗：

— 是

Notes: By the state as well.

↳ 制度化的处罚包括死刑吗：

— 是

↳ 制度化的处罚包括流放吗：

— 是

↳ 制度化的处罚包括体罚吗：

— 是

↳ 制度化的处罚包括排挤孤立吗：

— 是

↳ 制度化的处罚包括没收财产吗:

— 是

该宗教团体有正式的法典吗 :

— 否

Notes: Whether the monastic code could be considered a legal code is an interesting question, but the nonsectarian teachers didn't subscribe to a formal legal code different from the locales in which they lived.

宗教团体的信众受制于外部体制下的法典吗 :

— 是

Notes: From both the state and their own local monasteries.

福利

该宗教团体有体制化的军事力量吗 :

— 否

宗教团体的信众参加宗教团体以外机构提供的机制化的军事力量吗 :

— 否

Notes: Although occasionally monks would take up arms in local disputes, they were generally exempt from state drafts.

宗教团体的信众受保护或受治于宗教图案以外机构提供的机制化的军事力量吗 :

— 是

Notes: Broadly speaking the state military would defend the monasteries. However, when Gonpo Namgyel conquered Derge, it fell to many of the nonsectarian teachers, especially Kongtrul, to negotiate on behalf of the kingdom with the conquerors.

书面语

该宗教团体有自己独特的书面语吗 :

— 否

团体信众能在宗教团体以外的体制中接触到非宗教专用的书面语吗 :

— 是

Notes: Tibetan.

团体信众在宗教团体以外的体制下使用使用非宗教专用的书面语吗 :

— 是

Notes: On occasion, teachers would send letters, teachings, and so forth to secular rulers and officials.

日历

该宗教团体有正式的历法吗：

— 是

Notes: Tibetan monasteries and Tibet more broadly follow a lunar calendar that includes that monastic ritual calendar.

该宗教团体的信众在宗教团体以外的体制下有正式的历法可用吗：

— 否

Notes: I think of the lunar calendar as being provided by the monasteries for the state rather than the other way around.

食物生产

该宗教团体自产食物吗

— 否

Notes: While monasteries do own arable land and some are probably self-sufficient, they generally depend on donations, taxes, and offerings as well for their food supply.

该宗教团体外的机构向团体信众提供食物吗：

— 是

Notes: Laypeople and the state also donate or make offerings of food to monasteries.

请描述食物生产的形式/层级【多选】

— 畜牧

— 小规模农业/园艺花园或果园

— 大规模农业（比如，单一型农业作物制，组织化的灌溉系统）

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Tibetan Nonsectarianism (ris med), Aris, Michael. "Jamyang Khyentse's Brief Discourse on the Essence of All the Ways: A Work of the Ris-med Movement". Kailash 5 (January 1, 1977).

Reference: Tibetan Nonsectarianism (ris med), bral, Bdud 'joms Ye shes Rdo rje 'Jigs. The Nyingma School of Tibetan Buddhism. Simon and Schuster, 2012.

https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Nyingma_School_of_Tibetan_Buddhism.html?

hl=&id=5DI6AwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Tibetan Nonsectarianism (ris med), Kongtrul, Jamgon. *The Treasury of Knowledge: Book One*. Shambhala Publications, 2003.

[https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Treasury_of_Knowledge_Book_One.html?](https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Treasury_of_Knowledge_Book_One.html?hl=&id=5VFeAgAAQBAJ)

hl=&id=5VFeAgAAQBAJ.

Reference: Tibetan Nonsectarianism (ris med), Deroche, Marc-Henri. "On Being 'impartial'(ris Med): From Non-sectarianism to the Great Perfection". *Revue D'etudes Tibétaines* 44 (April 1, 2018).

Reference: Tibetan Nonsectarianism (ris med), Gayley, Holly, and Joshua Schapiro. *A Gathering of Brilliant Moons*. Simon and Schuster, 2017.

[https://books.google.com/books/about/A_Gathering_of_Brilliant_Moons.html?hl=&id=YOM7DwAAQBAJ.](https://books.google.com/books/about/A_Gathering_of_Brilliant_Moons.html?hl=&id=YOM7DwAAQBAJ)

Reference: Tibetan Nonsectarianism (ris med), Gardner, Alexander. *The Life of Jamgon Kongtrul the Great*. Shambhala Publications, 2019.

[https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Life_of_Jamgon_Kongtrul_the_Great.html?](https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Life_of_Jamgon_Kongtrul_the_Great.html?hl=&id=9jGgDwAAQBAJ)

hl=&id=9jGgDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Tibetan Nonsectarianism (ris med), Mathes, Klaus-Dieter, and Gabriele Coura. *Nonsectarianism (ris Med) in 19th- and 20th-century Eastern Tibet*. BRILL, 2021.

[https://books.google.com/books/about/Nonsectarianism_ris_med_in_19th_and_20th.html?](https://books.google.com/books/about/Nonsectarianism_ris_med_in_19th_and_20th.html?hl=&id=uzlIEAAAQBAJ)

hl=&id=uzlIEAAAQBAJ.

Reference: Tibetan Nonsectarianism (ris med), Tsomu, Yudru. *The Rise of Gönpo Namgyel in Kham*, 2014.

[https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Rise_of_G%C3%B6npö_Namgyel_in_Kham.html?](https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Rise_of_G%C3%B6npö_Namgyel_in_Kham.html?hl=&id=wU7YoQEACAAJ)

hl=&id=wU7YoQEACAAJ.

Reference: Tibetan Nonsectarianism (ris med), Tulku, Ringu. *The Ri-me Philosophy of Jamgon Kongtrul the Great*. Shambhala Publications, 2007.

[https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Ri_me_Philosophy_of_Jamgon_Kongtrul.html?](https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Ri_me_Philosophy_of_Jamgon_Kongtrul.html?hl=&id=p8l0QwI9gdcC)

hl=&id=p8l0QwI9gdcC.

Reference: Tibetan Nonsectarianism (ris med), Smith, E. Gene. "jam Mgon Kong Sprul and the Nonsectarian Movement". In *Among Tibetan Texts*, edited by Kurtis R. Schaeffer. Boston: Wisdom Publications, 2001.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: 我不知道, Yeh, Emily T.. *Taming Tibet: Landscape Transformation and the Gift of Chinese Development..* Cornell University Press, 2013.